

Original article

Perceived Effects of Job Stress on the Well-Being of Health Workers in Baruten Local Government Area Kwara State, Nigeria

I.I. Kperogi¹ *, J.F. James¹, A.M. Abdulraheem¹, I. Ologele¹, S.A. Adeoye², M.O. Ibrahim²

¹Department of Health Promotion and Environmental Health Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

²Department of Human Kinetics Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

ARTICLE INFO

Corresponding Email. kperogi.II@unilorin.edu.ng

Received: 02-09-2023

Accepted: 03-10-2023

Published: 07-10-2023

Keywords. Effects, Stress, Well-being, Employees and Job.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Background and aims. This study examined perceived effects of job stress on the well-being of Health Workers (HWs) in Baruten Local Government Area (L.G.A) Kwara State, Nigeria. Workplace stress is the harmful physical, mental or social responses that happens to employees when there is pressure of job demands against the amount of control employees have on meeting them. These has caused so many effects on general wellbeing of employees across the world. **Methods.** This study adopted descriptive survey research design. A researchers' structured questionnaire, which was validated and tested for reliability with 0.81r, was used for the study. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the research questions and hypotheses. Hypotheses I and II respectively stated that HWs in the L.G.A, do not significantly perceive that job stress have effects on their physical, mental and social wellbeing. **Results.** Hypotheses I and II respectively has a calculated chi-square value of 294.16 which is greater than table value of 16.92 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val) and a calculated chi-square value of 361.82 which is greater than table value of 16.92 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val) all @ 9 degree of freedom. This shows that the two hypotheses were all rejected, implying that HWs significantly perceive that job stress have effects on their physical, mental and social wellbeing. **Conclusion.** Conclusively, HWs in the L.G.A, perceive that job stress affects their general wellbeing. Recommendations were drawn from the conclusion to include admonishing Baruten L.G.A management to urgently work towards improving workers' ability to cope and manage stressful situations through stress management programs among others.

Cite this article. Kperogi I, James J, Abdulraheem A, Ologele I, Perceived Effects of Job Stress on the Well-Being of Health Workers in Baruten Local Government Area Kwara State, Nigeria. *Alq J Med App Sci.* 2023;6(2):584-592.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8417515>

INTRODUCTION

Workers in places of their respective jobs get exposed to various levels of stress which affects their wellbeing. The health care employees in their various places of work are not exempted in this plight. Prolonged and excessive stress can have many and various negative impacts on our mental, physical and social wellbeing. While some employees who are seen as highest performers can often survive and thrive in stressful environments, stress remains overwhelming and

damaging for some of us [6]. The adverse effects of workplace stress can take many forms, including the following: Unhealthy eating habit; Recreational drug use; Burnout and Negative effects at the company level. Unhealthy eating habit among employees, in which research shows that stress impacts not only our physiology, but also our behavior. High levels of stress can be associated with both increased (e.g., saturated fat consumption) and decreased (e.g., overall calories) food intake. Studies in adolescents and adults have also shown they consume more snacks when stressed up at job places [4].

Recreational drug use is another effect of job place stress. Stress can be associated with a marked increase in recreational drug use (legal ones like alcohol, nicotine, and caffeine) and illegal (like heroin and cocaine). While the exact reasons for the association may vary, they may include the belief that drug use can reduce stress. Further complicating matters, physical and psychological reactions to abstaining from previously self-administered drugs can increase stress as a symptom of withdrawal [4]. Burnout & workplace stress is another situation where by, prolonged stress in the workplace often leads to burnout and is peculiar to suppliers of critical services to the public. During natural disasters or health crises, healthcare and emergency service workers often work long hours over many days and weeks, reporting severe psychological distress [9]. Burnout is an occupational phenomenon where employees experience a mix of physical and psychological symptoms that result in decreased job satisfaction and productivity [3]. Nowadays, burnout is not limited to only healthcare professionals, but can occur in any industry including academics. The World Health Organization, defined burnout as “a syndrome conceptualized as resulting from chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed” and this is what Health workers experience in their places of work almost on daily basis [17].

Negative effects on the company’s output is always recorded in a workplace where stress is uncontrolled among it workers. While stress can be harmful to the employees, it also has the potential to damage the company due to increased staff absence due to sickness, poor productivity, high turnover, low morale, poor motivation, and increased employee complaints [2]. If your job demands more than you can deliver, you could be experiencing workplace stress which should not be ignored [16]. According to the American Psychological Association, “everyone who has had a job has, at some point, felt the pressure of work-related stress” [1]. While seemingly inevitable, we can do much to prevent stress and reduce its effects. This article explores many of the causes and introduces practical measures that helps.

Stress at work has many causes, often specific to the individual and the workplace. Common workplace stressors include: Longer working hours impacting work–life balance; Job insecurity; Low salary; Excessive and tiring commutes; Increasing work demands; Unrealistic deadlines; Limited opportunities for growth, development, or advancement; Challenging or difficult colleagues; Too many meetings; Email overload; Incompetent or uncaring managers and supervisors; Meaningless targets; Constantly changing technology; Lack of social support; Insufficient control over job-related decisions; Conflicting job demands and unclear performance expectations; In most cases, multiple stressors combine to produce our work-related stress, differing in severity through the day and even our career [1] & [12]. Physical symptoms of stress include: Aches and pains; Chest pain or a feeling like your heart is racing; Exhaustion or trouble sleeping; Headaches; dizziness or shaking; High blood pressure; Muscle tension or jaw clenching; Stomach or digestive problems; Trouble having sex; heartburn; Constipation or diarrhea; tiredness, slow reactions, shortness of breath among others. More so, workplace stress has a significant impact on the incidence and duration of depression. However, research has found that improving workers’ ability to cope and manage stressful situations through stress management programs (including cognitive-behavioral approaches) reduces absence rates due to sickness and staff turnover, and eases depressive symptoms among workers [8]. Examples of minimizing stress exposure include seeking professional help when needed, engaging in self-care activities, and talking with colleagues about their experiences and concerns. Doing so can help alleviate job stress and improve the well-being among healthcare workers and other workers across the globe.

National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) reported that cardiovascular disease in many studies suggest that psychologically demanding jobs that allow employees little control over the work process increase the risk of cardiovascular disease. On the basis of Musculoskeletal Disorders research by NIOSH and many other organizations, it is widely believed that job stress increases the risk for development of back and upper- extremity musculoskeletal disorders [11]. Several studies on Psychological Disorders suggest that differences in rates of mental health problems (such as depression and burnout) for various occupations are due partly to differences in job stress levels. (Economic and lifestyle differences between occupations may also contribute to some of these problems.) Although more study on Workplace Injury is needed, there is a growing concern that stressful working conditions interfere with safe work practices and set the stage for injuries at work. Some studies on Suicide, Cancer, Ulcers, and Impaired Immune Function

suggest a relationship between stressful working conditions and these health problems. However, more research is needed before firm conclusions can be drawn [11].

Commonly observed physical symptoms include high blood pressure, a fast pulse, Cheyne Stokes respiration, headache, and tense muscles. Mental health symptoms may involve irritability, tension, aggressive behaviors, lack of concentration, and sleep, perception, and memory disorders. The development of such physical and mental health problems can also lead to extended sick leaves or absenteeism and decreases in job quality, performance, and productivity; it can also threaten workers' health and safety [13].

Psychological symptoms and effects are the major consequences of stress. Then mental health of employees is threatened by high levels of stress and poor mental health. Unlike the Physical symptoms, psychological symptoms could also cause employees work performance to deteriorate. Anger, anxiety, depression, nervousness, irritability, aggressiveness, and boredom results in low employee performance, declines in self-esteem, resentment of supervision, inability to concentrate, trouble in making decision and job dissatisfaction. Also, the psychological symptoms of stress can lead to burnout. Job burnout is a prolonged withdrawal from work which makes the sufferer devalue his work and sees it as a source of dissatisfaction. Behavioral symptoms and effects of stress include eating more or less, cigarette smoking, used of alcohol and drugs, rapid speech pattern nervous fidgeting which leads to absenteeism from work, hopping from job to job and causes performance to deteriorate [5].

Stress at the workplace has been recognized as a global disease due to its negative impact on the physical, emotional and psychological well-being of people in various occupational groups [7]. Anxiety or depression was described by 30% of workers in the health care sectors particularly among those in the hospitals [14]. Studies in low-and middle-income countries among primary health-care professionals suggest that burnout is substantial, mainly because of the workforce shortages in the countries. Estimates ranged from 2.55 for severe burnout among family physicians in China to 87% for burnout in Uganda [10]. The statistics is not different from the experiences health care workers have in Nigeria, with particular focus on Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State, hence the need to carry out this study.

Considering justification and statement of the problem for this research, job stress among Health Workers particularly in hospitals, has become a growing concern. Studies have shown that job stress can lead to health problems, decreased job performance, and decreased well-being in general. The effect of job stress on physical health can increase the risk of developing chronic health conditions such as heart disease, obesity, diabetes, and high blood pressure. In addition, job stress has been linked to musculoskeletal disorders, digestion problems, decreased immunity, and other physical ailments. The effect of job stress is on mental health has been linked to depression, anxiety, burnout, and other mental health issues. Furthermore, job stress has the potentials to cause poorer cognitive performance, decreased job satisfaction, and decreased engagement in the workplace.

Job stress potentially has effects on the general well-being of Health Workers, which may also have negative impacts on social relationships with family, friends, and colleagues. Overall, job stress has a negative effect on the well-being of Health Workers, particularly, as observed in Baruten L.G.A by the researchers. Stress apparently leads to physical and mental health issues, as well as issues with social relationships to even patients in the hospitals. It is important for Health workers to be aware of the negative effects of job stress and to take steps towards minimizing their exposure to it. Often time, workplace stress particularly in hospitals have remained unchecked over time. Health workers are seen working round the year without been able to access their entitled annual leave allowances, which is expected to be used during leave period to ease accumulated stress by visiting stress relieve facilities like vacation centers among others. These has led to numerous health issues that sometimes leads to terminal diseases like Stroke, Depression, diabetes among others. It is on this note that the researchers deemed it fit to examine the perceived effects of job stress among Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria.

Research questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the present study.

1. Do Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, of Kwara State Nigeria, perceive that job stress affects their physical wellbeing?
2. Do Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, of Kwara State Nigeria, perceive that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were postulated to guide the study.

1. Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, of Kwara State Nigeria, do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their physical wellbeing.
2. Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, of Kwara State Nigeria, do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing.

METHODS

Study design and setting

A descriptive research design of survey type was used for this study. The population of this study comprises all Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, of Kwara State Nigeria, cutting across all the four (4) Districts in Baruten.

Data collection procedure

A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to draw two hundred and sixty-eight (268) sampled respondents for this study. At stage one, the researchers employed stratified sampling technique on the already existing four (4) Districts in Baruten L.G.A. (Gwanara, Ilesha, Okuta and Yashikira).

At stage two, the researcher employed simple random sampling technique of raffle draw at each District, where the names of Hospitals were placed in a device, spanned thoroughly, before four (4) research assistants were made to select twenty-three (23) Hospitals out of Sixty-Three (63) across the four districts in Baruten L.G.A, one after the other.

The third stage involved the use of Purposive sampling technique, where only Health Workers (Nurses, Community Health Workers, Pharmacists and Health Information Officers) in the selected Hospitals across the four (4) Districts were involved as respondents for the study. Finally, at stage four, the researchers employed convenience sampling technique to select all Health Workers who were present at the selected Hospitals across the four (4) Districts, at the time of the study, to get a total of two hundred and sixty-eight (268) respondents for the study. Table 1 below shows the breakdown of the sampling procedure.

Table 1. Sample size from selected Hospitals in Baruten L.G.A.

S/N	Selected Districts	Selected Hospitals	Number of respondents in the selected Hospitals	Total Respondents used
1.	Gwanara	General Hospital Gwanara, L.G.A Dispensary Gwanara, L.G.A. Dispensary Gobo, L.G.A. Dispensary Ningurumi, L.G.A. Dispensary Kero, L.G.A. Dispensary Yakiru	13 12 9 10 9 8	61
2.	Ilesha	General Hospital Ilesha, L.G.A. Dispensary Ilesha, L.G.A. Dispensary Tumboya, L.G.A. Dispensary Bode/Babane, L.G.A. Dispensary Shinawu,	15 15 11 12 12	65
3.	Okuta	General Hospital Okuta, L.G.A. Dispensary Okuta, Mobile Hospital Okuta, L.G.A. Dispensary Kenu, L.G.A. Dispensary Boriya, L.G.A. Dispensary Shiya,	13 10 13 12 11 10	69
4.	Yashikira	Maternal and Child health Care Kosubosu, Basic Health Care Centre Gure, L.G.A., Dispensary Chikanda, L.G.A. Dispensary Gwane, L.G.A. Dispensary Yashikiru, L.G.A. Dispensary Gwasoro	15 13 13 13 10 9	73
	Total	23	268	268

Source: Department of Medical and Health, Baruten L.G.A, Kwara Sate, Nigeria (2023).

A researcher - developed questionnaire was used for the study. The questionnaire consists of two sections namely: Section A and B. Section A elicited the socio-demographic information of the respondents while section B contains items on the postulated hypotheses for the respondents. The respond mode was based on four-point Likert rating scale format with the scores of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) =3, Strongly Disagree (SD) =2 and Disagree (D) =1 was used. The research instrument was validated by three experts in the Department of Health Promotion and Environmental Health Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. The researchers adopted the split-half method to determine reliability of research instrument by administration of twenty questionnaires to Health Workers in Ilorin West L.G.A. Kwara State, Nigeria, which is not the same as the study area. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to obtain 0.81r which is reliable enough for the study. Demographic data of the respondents were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and simple percentage and inferential statistics of chi-square to analyze the stated hypotheses, at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their physical wellbeing.

Table 2. Chi-square analysis on Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria not significantly perceiving that job stress affects their physical wellbeing

SN	Items	Sa	A	D	Sd	Row Total	dF	Cal Value	Table Value	Remarks
1	Long work hours of health workers can have effects on their physical wellbeing (Headache or Insomnia).	174 (64.9%)	63 (23.5%)	16 (6.0%)	15 (5.6%)	268				
2	Poor salaries increase bad eating habit which have effects on physical wellbeing (junks causing Obesity or Diabetes).	159 (59.3%)	74 (27.6%)	25 (9.3%)	10 (3.7%)	268				
3	Changing technologies causing stress, can have effects on physical wellbeing of workers by accidents.	91 (34.0%)	147 (54.9%)	20 (7.5%)	10 (3.7%)	268	9	294.16	16.92	Ho rejected
4	Recreational drug use is an effect of job place stress.	157 (58.6%)	76 (28.4%)	15 (5.6%)	20 (7.5%)	268				
	Total	312	312	118	58	1072				

@ 0.05 alpha level of significance

Table 2 shows that hypothesis one Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their physical wellbeing. The hypothesis which has a calculated chi-square value of 294.16 is greater than chi-square table value of 16.92 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val) @ 9 degree of freedom. This shows that the hypothesis was rejected which implies that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria significantly, perceive that job stress affects their physical wellbeing.

Hypothesis 2: Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing,

Table 3. Chi-square analysis on Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria not significantly perceiving that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing

Sn	Items	Sa	A	D	Sd	Row total	dF	Cal value	Table value	Remarks
1	Depression and anxiety are effects of job stress is on mental health.	177 (66.0%)	54 (20.1%)	27 (10.1%)	10 (3.7%)	268				
2	Psychological symptoms that results in decreased job satisfaction are effects of stress.	103 (37.4%)	133 (49.6%)	10 (3.7%)	22 (8.2%)	268				
3	Job stress has effects on social relationships with family and friends.	169 (63.1%)	69 (25.7%)	20 (7.5%)	10 (3.7%)	268	9	361.82	16.92	Ho rejected
4	Self-administration of drugs is an effect of job stress.	183 (68.3%)	53 (19.8%)	20 (5.7%)	12 (4.5%)	268				
	Total	322	292	126	58	1072				

@ 0.05 alpha level of significance

Table 3 shows that hypothesis one which stated that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing. The hypothesis which has a calculated chi-square value of 361.82 is greater than chi-square table value of 16.92 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val) @ 9 degree of freedom. This shows that the hypothesis was rejected which implies that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria, significantly perceive that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing.

DISCUSSION

Hypothesis one which stated that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria, do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their physical wellbeing, was rejected. This is because the calculated chi-square value of 294.16, is greater than the table value of 16.92 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val) @ 9 degree of freedom. This implies that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria, significantly perceive that job stress have effects on their physical wellbeing. In line with the findings from this study [13], reported that, commonly observed physical symptoms include high blood pressure, a fast pulse, Cheyne Stokes respiration, headache, and tense muscles. Mental health symptoms may involve irritability, tension, aggressive behaviors, lack of concentration, and sleep, perception, and memory disorders. The development of such health problems can also lead to extended sick leaves or absenteeism and decreases in job quality, performance, and productivity; it can also threaten workers' health and safety.

This finding is in conformity with the report of [7], who reported that stress at the workplace has been recognized as a global disease due to its negative impact on the physical, emotional and psychological well-being of people in various occupational groups. In line with this finding, [16], also reported that if your job demands becomes more than you can deliver, you could be experiencing workplace stress. Apparently, this have being the case among health workers, particularly in Baruten L.G, A, whose job demands stretch their ability, without due consideration to their wellbeing.

Hypothesis two which stated that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria, do not significantly perceive that job stress affects their mental and social wellbeing was rejected. This is because the calculated chi-square value of 361.82, is greater than the table value of 16.92 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val) @ 9 degree of freedom. This implies that Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria, significantly perceive that job stress have effects on their mental and social wellbeing. This finding is in line with the postulation of [14], who reported that Anxiety or depression was described by 30% of workers in the health care sectors. Furthermore, [2], reported in consonance with this finding that while stress can be harmful to the employee, it also has the potential to damage the company due to increased staff

absence due to sickness, poor productivity, low morale, poor motivation, and increased employee complaints. This finding is exactly what health workers experiences in Hospitals, without any course to ameliorate the effects on their wellbeing.

[5], also reported in lined that psychological symptoms and effects are the major consequences of stress. Then mental health of employees is threatened by high levels of stress and poor mental health. Unlike the Physical symptoms, psychological symptoms could also cause employees work performance to deteriorate. Anger, anxiety, depression, nervousness, irritability, aggressiveness, and boredom results in low employee performance, declines in self-esteem, resentment of supervision, inability to concentrate, trouble in making decision and job dissatisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Health workers in Baruten L.G.A of Kwara State Nigeria, perceive that job stress have effects on their physical wellbeing which emanates from their job schedules in hospitals.

Health workers in Baruten L.G.A, of Kwara State Nigeria, perceive that job stress have effects on their mental and social wellbeing, during their practice of health care delivery processes in hospitals.

Recommendations

The management of Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria, should as a matter of urgency work towards improving workers' ability to cope and manage stressful situations through stress management programs (including cognitive-behavioral approaches).

Revive the consciousness of health care workers on the need to participate actively in preventing workplace stress, and its attendant complicating effects on their general wellbeing in Baruten L.G.A, Kwara State Nigeria.

Social relationships are vital in improving cardiovascular health and immune functions and reducing rates of anxiety and depression hence the need to sensitize health workers towards that consciousness.

Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

Data availability statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation if required.

Ethics statements

Within the scope of the study, data were collected with the permission of the ethics committee of Department of Medical and Health Baruten L.G.A, Kwara Sate Nigeria, with the decision dated 13.11.2022 and numbered 2022.077.

Author contributions

I.I Kperogi, served as corresponding author, helped plan and execute the study, conducted data analysis and wrote large portions of the manuscript. J.F. James helped plan and execute the study and conducted data analysis. A.M. Abdulraheem also helped plan and execute the study and conducted data analysis. I. Ologele helped plan and execute the study and wrote large portions of the manuscript. S.A. Adeoye helped plan and execute the study and wrote large portions of the manuscript. M.O. Ibrahim helped plan and execute the study and wrote large portions of the manuscript. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

REFERENCES

1. American Psychological Association (APA). Coping with stress at work. APA 2018. (Cited 2023 Apr 10). Available from: <http://www.apa.org/topics/healthy-workplaces/work-stress>.
2. Attridge D. Effects of work-related stress. University of Cambridge Human Resources 2021. Retrieved 2021, Aug 26, from <https://www.hr.admin.cam.ac.uk/policies-procedures/managing-stress-and-promoting-wellbeing-work-policy/policy-statement/effects>.
3. Bridgeman P, Bridgeman B, Barone J. Burnout syndrome among healthcare professionals. *The Bulletin of the American Society of Hospital Pharmacists*. 2018;75(3), 147–152.
4. Contrada J, Baum A. *The handbook of stress science: Biology, psychology, and health*. Springer 2011.

5. Dwamena M. Stress and its Effects on Employees Productivity – A case study of Ghana Ports and Harbours Authority, Takoradi. A Thesis submitted to the Institute of Distance Learning Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Commonwealth Executive Master of Business Administration 2012, June.
6. Kovacs M. Stress and coping in the workplace. The British Psychological Society 2007. Cited 2021 Aug. Available from: <https://thepsychologist.bps.org.uk/volume-20/edition-9/stress-and-coping-workplace>
7. Kruspal J, Bhautik M, Sanjay S, Sanjay G. Occupational Stress among Health Care Workers. Identifying Occupational Stress and Coping Strategies 2022. Submitted: August 22nd, 2022 to Open Access Peer-Review, Reviewed: 2022 August 25th. Published: October 3rd, 2022. DOI:10.5772/intechopen.107397.
8. Mino Y, Babazono A, Tsuda T, Yasuda N. Can Stress Management at the Workplace Prevent Depression? A randomized controlled trial. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*, 2006; 75(3), 177–182.
9. Moss J. Rethinking burnout. In *HBR guide to beating burnout*. 2021;1–13. Harvard Business Review Press 2021.
10. Muliira R, Ssendikadiwa B. Professional quality of life and associated factors among Ugandan midwives working in Mubende and Mityana rural district. *Maternal and Child Health Journal* 2016. 2016;20:567-576.
11. National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH). Stress At Work. Publications & Products NIOSH-Issued Publications 2014. Centers for Diseases Control and Prevention (CDC). Cited from <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/index.htm>
12. Neenan M. Developing resilience: A cognitive-behavioural approach. Routledge 2018.
13. Ornek O, Esin M. Effects of a Work-Related Stress Model Based Mental Health Promotion Program on Job Stress, Stress Reactions and Coping Profiles of Women Workers: A control groups study. *BMC Public Health* 2020;(20), Cited 2023, Jul. 23rd from https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-020-09769-0#auth-Ozlem_Koseoglu-Ornek
14. Prasad K, McLoughlin C, Stillman M, Poplau S, Goelz E, Taylor S, et, al. Prevalence and correlates of stress and burnout among U.S. healthcare workers during the Covid-19 pandemic: A National Cross-Sectional Survey Study. *E Clinical Medicine* 2021. 2021;35:100879.
15. Quick J, Henderson D. Occupational stress: Preventing Suffering, Enhancing Wellbeing. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 2016. 2016;13(5),459.
16. Schwartz T, McCarthy C. Manage your energy not your time. In *HBR guide to managing stress at work* 2014. 2014;53–80. Harvard Business Review Press.
17. World Health Organization (WHO). Burn-out an “Occupational Phenomenon”: International classification of diseases 2019. Cited from https://www.who.int/mental_health/evidence/burn-out/en/ on 2023 May, 26th.

التأثيرات الملموسة لضغوط العمل على رفاهية العاملين الصحيين في منطقة الحكومة المحلية في باروتين، ولاية كوارا، نيجيريا

I.I. Kperogi¹*, J.F. James¹, A.M. Abdulraheem¹, I. Ologele¹, S.A. Adeoye², M.O. Ibrahim²

¹قسم تعزيز الصحة والتثقيف في مجال الصحة البيئية، كلية التربية، جامعة إيلورين، إيلورين، نيجيريا

²قسم تعليم حركة الإنسان، كلية التربية، جامعة إيلورين، إيلورين، نيجيريا؛

المستخلص

الخلفية والأهداف. تناولت هذه الدراسة التأثيرات الملحوظة لضغوط العمل على رفاهية العاملين الصحيين (HWs) في منطقة الحكومة المحلية باروتين (L.G.A) بولاية كوارا، نيجيريا. الإجهاد في مكان العمل هو الاستجابات الجسدية أو العقلية أو الاجتماعية الضارة التي تحدث للموظفين عندما يكون هناك ضغط من متطلبات الوظيفة مقابل مقدار سيطرة الموظفين على تلبية تلك المتطلبات. وقد تسبب ذلك في العديد من التأثيرات على الرفاهية العامة للموظفين في جميع أنحاء العالم. **طرق الدراسة.** اعتمدت هذه الدراسة تصميم البحث المسحي الوصفي. تم استخدام استبيان منظم للباحثين، والذي تم التحقق من صحته واختبار موثوقيته بـ $r=0.81$ ، في الدراسة. وتم استخدام الإحصاء الوصفي والاستنتاجي لتحليل أسئلة البحث وفرضياته. ذكرت الفرضيتين الأولى والثانية على التوالي أن العاملين في مجال الصحة في L.G.A، لا يدركون بشكل كبير أن ضغوط العمل لها آثار على صحتهم الجسدية والعقلية والاجتماعية. **النتائج.** تحتوي الفرضيتين الأولى والثانية على التوالي على قيمة مربع كاي محسوبة تبلغ 294.16 وهي أكبر من القيمة الجدولية البالغة 16.92 ($\chi^2_{val} > Tab \chi^2_{val}$) وقيمة مربع كاي المحسوبة 361.82 وهي أكبر من القيمة الجدولية البالغة 16.92 ($\chi^2_{val} > Tab \chi^2_{val}$) @ 9 درجة من الحرية. وهذا يدل على أن الفرضيتين قد تم رفضهما جميعاً، مما يعني أن العاملين في مجال الصحة يدركون بشكل كبير أن ضغوط العمل لها آثار على صحتهم الجسدية والعقلية والاجتماعية. **الخاتمة.** بشكل قاطع، يرى العمال في L.G.A أن ضغوط العمل تؤثر على رفاهيتهم العامة. تم استخلاص التوصيات من الاستنتاج لتشمل تحذير إدارة Baruten L.G.A للعمل بشكل عاجل على تحسين قدرة العمال على التعامل مع المواقف العصيبة وإدارتها من خلال برامج إدارة الإجهاد وغيرها.

الكلمات الدالة. التأثيرات والإجهاد والرفاهية والموظفين والوظيفة.